

Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows

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20 December 2024

Imprint

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Date of publication	20 December 2024
Version	Version 1.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267446
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Deliverable	D4.2 Concept for Sustainable PID Registration Workflows

About

PID4NFDI is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (**Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI**). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through **Base4NFDI**.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. Grant Number: [521466146](#)

Funded by

Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft
German Research Foundation

Contents

Background	1
Introduction	2
Framework conditions for an efficient and sustainable PID management within NFDI	3
Gaps and Challenges	3
Recommendations for Financing a Sustainable PID Management	4
Organisational Requirements for Sustainable PID Adoption	6
Developing a PID Selection and Integration Framework	9
Communication and Coordination	9
Transparency and POSI Principles	9
Supporting Adoption through Coordination	10
Supporting a Federated Model for PID Management	10
Iterative Coordination and Support	11
Establishing the PID Coordination Hub Takes Time	11
Long-Term Vision for the PID Coordination Hub	11
Tasks of the PID Coordination Hub	11
Overview of Components	11
Providing a PID Selection Guide	12
Existing Model 1: FREYA Guides to Choosing PIDs	12
Existing Model 2: PIDwijzer	14
Conclusion	15
References	16

Background

PID4NFDI¹ is a foundational service for persistent identifiers (PIDs) being developed for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI – Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur²). Funded as part of Base4NFDI,³ the project seeks to establish a sustainable and robust framework for PIDs within the NFDI ecosystem. Work Package 4 focuses on analyzing and documenting the governance, business, and license models of various PID providers and types, including an assessment of their risks and corresponding mitigation strategies using frameworks like POSI. This effort prioritizes models from project partners and other widely used PID services identified in earlier analyses within Work Packages 1 and 2.

The insights gained will inform the development of a decision model during the integration phase of PID4NFDI (beginning in January 2025), designed to evaluate the benefits, challenges, and costs of different PID approaches tailored to the diverse use cases within the NFDI consortia. The document provides context for the data compiled in the overview of PID providers and types,⁴ with both forming **Deliverable 4.1**⁵ of PID4NFDI during the initialization phase.

Building on this foundation, Work Package 4 also aims to develop a concept for sustainable PID registration workflows that align with the NFDI's governance and funding structure. By identifying organizational and financial gaps and opportunities, the project will propose pathways to ensure the sustainable adoption of PID registration processes. The ultimate goal is to promote the strategic and long-term implementation of PIDs through sound governance, informed decision-making, and sustainable infrastructure. The following concept is presented as **Deliverable 4.2** of PID4NFDI.

¹ <http://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/>

² <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

³ <https://base4nfdi.de/>

⁴ PID4NFDI Overview of PID providers and types:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BvKmKij2WONCWheFTDnr2g3cGw3z5alZ9G2_qVCFpRk/edit

⁵ Hagemann-Wilholt, Kahlert (2024). D4.1 Contextualizing the Overview of PID Providers and Types.

Introduction

Based on the overview of PID providers and types and its contextualization (D4.1), the NFDI PID practices landscape⁶, and use-case analyses,⁷ we are deriving a concept for the sustainable management of PIDs for the NFDI as a holistic governance approach. Designing a governance concept for integrating PID services in NFDI requires a careful balance between centralized coordination and flexibility for the diverse, discipline- and resource-specific needs of NFDI consortia. In the following, the key issues to consider and approaches to manage the fragmented landscape of PID providers and the NFDI structure are presented.

The vision for an established PID Coordination Hub is to create a central service that provides orientation on existing PID solutions and standards while promoting cross-disciplinary alignment through clear policies and guidelines. This hub shall be a central point of contact for all questions relating to PIDs. It will serve as a knowledge base, offering documentation, training, and tools to support researchers and institutions in integrating PIDs into the research data lifecycle. It will address both fundamental questions about the benefits of PIDs and complex challenges, such as incorporating multiple and emerging PIDs into workflows.

Recognizing that persistence is not merely a technical requirement but also the result of the interplay between technology, governance, finances, organizational processes, and interoperability standards, the hub will foster awareness and transparency. Sustainability will be ensured by making the conditions for persistence explicit, addressing key aspects such as business and governance models, technical contributions, and the responsibilities of all stakeholders in maintaining a robust and reliable PID infrastructure.

⁶ El-Gebali et al. (2024): D1.1 Landscape of PID practices.

⁷ Four use case analyses were published as reports. Those on StrainInfo and the one on FAIRagro were published by Sara El-Gebali. The use case analyses on Text+ and KonsortSWD were published by Jana Böhm. See the reference list at the end of the document for full citations.

Framework conditions for an efficient and sustainable PID management within NFDI

Gaps and Challenges

The current landscape of PID providers, which offer solutions for various use cases and communities, presents some fundamental challenges for the sustainable and efficient use of PIDs within NFDI. The structures of the PID provider landscape and NFDI pose significant challenges. The PID provider landscape is fragmented, with providers offering solutions of varying maturity levels tailored to different communities and use cases under diverse conditions. The PID providers operate on different technological foundations (e.g., handle-based or PURL-based PIDs). They exhibit varying levels of maturity, both technically and organizationally: some providers offer a comprehensive portfolio of technical tools and accompanying services for usage, while others are still in the development phase.

The level of interoperability with other services varies, as do the metadata requirements and challenges.⁸ Some providers have established collaborations with others that have been in place for years. We observe a variety of membership models that require differing levels of organizational and financial commitment from members and may target different audiences. Ideally, the governance models of the providers should reflect the goal of ensuring persistence through the use of their identifiers. However, in some cases, these governance models are not transparent or even accessible to potential customers.

The project-based funding structure of the NFDI, where organizations collaborate in various constellations around thematic focal points, is contradictory to the approach of PID providers, which aim to define long-term responsibilities for PID management.⁹ In the NFDI consortia, services are operated or planned that are either hosted by a single organization or collaboratively developed by multiple organizations. Especially in the latter case, it is crucial to plan responsibilities for sustainable PID management early on – technically, organizationally, and financially.

A study on PIDs conducted by Knowledge Exchange (KE)¹⁰ – a European network of key stakeholders within the research landscape – identified several risks associated with the creation of dysfunctional PIDs. These include the discontinuation of services, such as PID providers or minting infrastructure ceasing operations or operating under drastically different conditions (for instance, PID

⁸ Mathiak et al. (2024).

⁹ On risks and challenges of PID management within NFDI see also Bingert et al. (2022); see also the proposals for the project PID4NFDI: Bertelmann et al. (2024). Proposal for the Initialisation Phase of Base4NFDI and Bingert et al. (2024). Proposal for the Integration Phase of Base4NFDI.

¹⁰ Germany is represented by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG). For more information on KE, see: <https://www.knowledge-exchange.info/>.

provider services acquired by proprietary companies or repository services that are entirely discontinued). Additional risks involve insufficient financial support, limited community engagement, and low adoption rates – such as users failing to recognize the benefits of integrating and using PIDs. Technical and metadata challenges, including inadequate metadata quality and a lack of scalability in technical infrastructure, also contribute to the potential for dysfunctional PIDs.¹¹

Our survey results confirm that the project-based funding of many infrastructure services, along with the resulting lack of long-term personnel resources, poses a significant challenge for PID management. Additionally, there are growing and shifting technical and metadata requirements to accommodate an increasing number of use cases. In most cases, there is no clear budget for registering and managing PIDs as direct costs and staff efforts. Our survey reveals that the use of PIDs has primarily concentrated on the later stages of the research(data) lifecycle, while early planning for their implementation has often been neglected in NFDI consortia so far.¹²

However, we also see a growing awareness of the importance of integrating PIDs into workflows containing the creation of research data. This supports reducing the effort required for subsequent metadata curation, efficiently improves provenance information, and enables their use for a wider variety of entities.

We have identified three essential conditions for establishing a sustainable framework to enhance PID management within **NFDI: (1) securing stable financing** for PIDs, **(2) meeting organizational requirements**, and – as core responsibilities of the PID4NFDI Coordination Hub – (3) promoting **information sharing and coordination** among stakeholders to increase awareness and community engagement.

Recommendations for Financing a Sustainable PID Management

To address finance-related challenges as one of the main obstacles to manage PIDs, the following recommended actions should be considered:

Incorporating PID costs into budgets: Project budgets should explicitly allocate resources for minting and managing PIDs as direct costs. This approach ensures that the financial aspects of PID utilization are recognized upfront. Consider the explicit allocation of PID costs in funding proposals and the development of standardized budget templates that include fields for PID minting and management costs.

Integrating PIDs early in the research lifecycle: Embedding PIDs into workflows from the early stages of research ensures consistent metadata creation and

¹¹ de Castro et al. (2023), pp. 36-43.

¹² El-Gebali et al. (2024): D1.1 Landscape of PID practices.

reduces downstream efforts. This foresight avoids expensive retrofitting and supports FAIR principles. This can be supported by integrating PIDs into data management plans (DMPs). Providing researchers with tools and training to incorporate Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) into data collection and documentation workflows facilitates their early adoption. Furthermore, implementing PID policies and offering incentives to reward early adoption helps promote the development of mature PID integration workflows.

Raising awareness among funders: Funders need to be made aware of the cost-effectiveness of PIDs in enhancing data discovery, reuse, and provenance tracking. Demonstrating how PIDs save costs in the long term by reducing data curation overhead can help justify their inclusion into funding models.

Long-term support by infrastructure service providers: The costs associated with maintaining PID infrastructure (e.g., updating metadata and ensuring system operability) should be treated as an ongoing investment by service providers. These costs often manifest as personnel expenses for technical and administrative support. In an ideal world, establishing centralized or collaborative funding mechanisms would enable the efficient distribution of these costs.

Cost-benefit analyses conducted in Australia and the UK have demonstrated that integrating PIDs into publication workflows can lead to significant cost savings. This is because the use of PIDs drastically reduces the time and effort required for metadata entry, maintenance, and correction – benefiting all stakeholders within the research ecosystem.¹³

Linking costs to reuse metrics: Encouraging repositories to develop metrics that quantify the reuse and impact of data associated with PIDs can help funders see the return on investment. Metrics tied to repository outputs, such as reuse statistics and citation tracking, can underscore the value added by PIDs. The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information advocates for making openness the default approach to managing research information, promoting fairness and transparency in research assessment. Similarly, initiatives like Make Data Count aim to advance the adoption of open data metrics, integrating these metrics into research evaluations. Both efforts strongly support the effective use of PIDs as foundational tools to ensure FAIR research data management and metrics.¹⁴

Re-use existing PID publishing services: Institutions with limited budgets or low demand for PIDs can leverage established repositories that offer PID minting and management services. Repository services that bundle PID minting with quality assurance and metadata curation should be used primarily. Existing registries like

¹³ Brown et al. (2021); Brown et al. (2022).

¹⁴ Barcelona Declaration (2024); <https://makedatacount.org/>.

re3data.org for research data repositories offer support in identifying PID-supportive data repositories.¹⁵

Organisational Requirements for Sustainable PID Adoption

Recognize Persistence as a Multi-Component Requirement Framework

Persistence is not solely a technical issue. It also depends on the coordinated integration of multiple interrelated factors working together to ensure the lasting reliability and effectiveness of PID systems. From a **technical** perspective, this means establishing robust, scalable, and secure infrastructures equipped with redundancy mechanisms to prevent data loss and ensure system resilience. However, technical solutions alone are insufficient without **governance** structures that clearly define roles, responsibilities, and accountability for maintaining PIDs and ensuring their interoperability across diverse systems. **Financial sustainability** is another critical factor, requiring the creation of long-term funding models that provide consistent investment in PID infrastructure and associated services. On an **organizational** level, institutions must train staff and researchers to adopt standardized workflows that prioritize consistency, compliance, and the efficient use of PIDs throughout the research lifecycle. Finally, adherence to **standards and interoperability principles**, such as the FAIR data principles, is essential to ensure that PIDs integrate seamlessly into existing systems, maximizing their impact and usability. Together, these elements form a comprehensive framework for persistence, highlighting the need for awareness and collaboration across all stakeholders to maintain the integrity and functionality of PID systems over time.

To ensure the sustainable management of PIDs, a structured organizational framework is essential. This framework should address roles, responsibilities, and processes across the technical, governance, financial, and operational aspects of PID management.

PID Providers: Provide Transparent Information on Governance and Business Models

Ensuring transparency for sustainability is essential for fostering trust and long-term commitment in PID systems. To achieve this, business and governance models must clearly articulate the funding sources and the long-term financial commitments required to sustain PID services, assuring stakeholders that there are sufficient resources allocated for continued operations. Transparent governance structures are also necessary, providing detailed information on decision-making processes, accountability mechanisms, and how stakeholders will be involved in ongoing discussions and improvements. From a technical perspective, it is crucial to regularly update stakeholders on the technical health

¹⁵ E.g. query for filtering for repositories providing DOIs:
<https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&pidSystems%5B0%5D=DOI>

of PID systems, including uptime metrics, scalability capabilities, and any innovations that enhance system performance.

PID Providers: Document Workflows for PID Management

PID providers should create detailed, user-friendly guides that outline the steps of the PID lifecycle, such as instructions to generate PIDs, including templates for creating PIDs and best practices for providing appropriate metadata. They should provide protocols and guidelines for updating metadata and ensuring identifiers remain accurate and functional over time. Also, they should provide clear procedures to eliminate errors in the resolution process or for decommissioning PIDs when necessary, ensuring no disruption with associated data or resources. PID providers should compile examples of successful PID implementations that can serve as reference models.

Funding and Research Organizations: Establish PID Policies to Clarify Responsibilities

A significant challenge to the effective implementation of PIDs is the lack of well-defined **policies** regarding their management. Our survey indicates that within NFDI organizations, PID-related policies are often absent or insufficiently developed, leaving gaps in accountability and consistency. To address this issue, funders as well as research organizations must establish robust PID policies as part of their data management policies, funding agreements, and repository practices. Requirements should clearly define responsibilities and expectations on PID implementation and usage.

Figure 1: Responses to the question “Does your organization have a formal governance structure or committee dedicated to the management and oversight of PID policies and practices?” from PID4NFDI Landscape analysis. See: El-Gebali et al. (2024): D1.1 Landscape of PID Practices.

Funding agreements should mandate the inclusion of PID-related costs and practices in grant proposals and project budgets. Funders should offer subsidies to support consortia in integrating PIDs and aligning them with NFDI requirements and international standards. Statements on data management policies should require the use of PIDs as part of data sharing and preservation strategies. NFDI authorities should develop **incentives** for consortia to adopt PID best practices and align their activities with NFDI, as well as EOSC goals. The NFDI gains significant value from the extensive adoption of PIDs, as it boosts the FAIRness of research entities while showcasing and attributing its own impact and performance.

At the institutional level, policies should specify accountabilities for minting new PIDs, updating associated metadata, and ensuring their ongoing maintenance. This might include assigning long-term **responsibilities** to specific departments, such as libraries or IT services. Similarly, at the project level, researchers and project managers must understand their obligations regarding PID usage. **Clear requirements** from funders and employing organizations are particularly helpful here.

At the national level, specific guidelines for the use of PIDs are also still lacking. To address this gap, the PID Network Germany project is developing a roadmap that could form the basis for a comprehensive national PID policy. This framework may also serve as a reference for establishing a unified PID policy across NFDI. A critical aspect of this process is the inclusion of key NFDI stakeholders and authorities – such as the NFDI Association, funding agencies, sections, and consortia – to ensure broad alignment and effective implementation.¹⁶

PID4NFDI Coordination Hub: Raise Awareness and Leverage Use Case-Related Synergies

The PID4NFDI Coordination Hub aims to enhance the adoption and effective management of PIDs by leveraging synergies identified through diverse use cases across NFDI consortia and their related disciplines. By focusing on best practices, documentation, and process optimization, the hub will serve as a central resource to streamline PID integration into research workflows, fostering a cohesive and efficient approach to PID usage. We will work closely with use case partners to uncover successful strategies of PID selection and management. The goal is to document best practices that address common challenges, such as ensuring metadata quality, aligning with FAIR principles, and managing PIDs across different systems. This shared knowledge base will help NFDI communities to adopt proven workflows and to avoid unnecessary trial-and-error. Awareness and advocacy efforts should focus on educating stakeholders about the indispensable role of PIDs in research integrity, emphasizing how they contribute to ensuring the long-

¹⁶ For an overview of international PID policy initiatives see: <https://www.pid-network.de/network> (in German, linking to original sources).

term availability and accessibility of datasets and publications, thereby supporting sustainability across the research ecosystem.

Developing a PID Selection and Integration Framework

Building a PID Coordination Hub for NFDI requires a clear communication concept and ongoing coordination to ensure success. The following points outline the key measures for creating a robust framework to ensure the sustainable integration of PIDs into the NFDI.

Communication and Coordination

A robust communication strategy is vital to establish the PID Coordination Hub as the central point of contact for PID services and support within NFDI and beyond. The concept will include:

- **Target Audience Identification:** Defining key stakeholders such as repository managers, researchers, IT staff, and funding agencies.
- **Messaging Framework:** Developing clear, consistent messages about the benefits, functionality, and services offered by the PID Coordination Hub.
- **Channels and Tools:** Using newsletters, webinars, workshops, social media, and the PID Coordination Hub website to engage with stakeholders and provide updates.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Enabling users to share feedback, which can be used to refine the hub's services and resources.

Linking to a detailed communication concept¹⁷ document ensures stakeholders can access comprehensive plans for outreach and engagement.

Encouraging PID providers to offer transparent information on their business models, governance structures, and sustainability measures is essential for fostering trust and informed decision-making in the research community.

Transparency and POSI Principles

Establishing minimum standards for PID providers as critical information for selecting PIDs increases reliability and ensures compliance with FAIR principles, thereby ensuring the integrity of PIDs in the context of NFDI research data management.

¹⁷ PID4NFDI (2024): D 5.1 Communication strategy.

- **POSI Framework:** The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI)¹⁸ provide a benchmark for evaluating the trustworthiness and sustainability of PID providers. By encouraging providers to conduct self-assessments based on POSI, the PID Coordination Hub can help ensure that selected PIDs align with long-term sustainability, community governance, and openness.
- **Provider Accountability:** Transparent details about costs, funding sources, and governance give researchers and institutions confidence in the reliability and stability of the PID services they rely on.

Supporting Adoption through Coordination

- **Provider Engagement:** PID Coordination Hub can act as a mediator, engaging with PID providers to encourage the adoption of transparent practices. This includes organizing discussions, workshops, or surveys to highlight user needs and best practices.
- **User Empowerment:** By equipping users – researchers and institutions – with clear, comparable information on PID providers, the PID Coordination Hub empowers users to make informed decisions while promoting accountability among providers.
- **Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration:** Communities of Practice (CoPs) will be formed to address PID governance challenges, such as metadata harmonization and API standards, and to share best practices across disciplines. Collaboration with the NFDI working groups and sections on topics of metadata, terminology, training and interoperability will be key.¹⁹

Supporting a Federated Model for PID Management

The hub advocates for a decentralized, federated approach that respects the diversity of needs across NFDI consortia while maintaining overarching guidelines for interoperability and quality:

- **Consortium Flexibility:** Each consortium can select PIDs tailored to their needs, provided they adhere to NFDI standards, such as interoperability and FAIR compliance.
- **Crosswalks and Standards:** The hub will improve the discoverability and accessibility of mappings and crosswalks between PID standards, enabling more seamless translation and interoperability between systems.²⁰

¹⁸ For further details on POSI Principles see: Hagemann, Kahlert (2024): D4.1 Contextualizing the Overview of PID Providers and Types.

¹⁹ Kahlert, Hagemann-Wilholt (2024). D3.2 PID4NFDI Training Concept.

²⁰ El-Gebali (2024). Concepts for metadata interoperability, harmonization and technical integration.

Iterative Coordination and Support

Building the PID Coordination Hub is not a one-time effort. It demands ongoing collaboration and refinement:

- **Stakeholder Coordination:** Regular engagement with the NFDI consortia, PID providers, and international PID organizations to align goals and practices.
- **Iterative Improvement:** Continuously adapting services, tools, and resources based on user feedback and evolving requirements in the research landscape.
- **Training and Support:** Offering sustained guidance through workshops, helpdesk services, and user documentation to encourage widespread adoption and effective use of PIDs.

Establishing the PID Coordination Hub Takes Time

Positioning PID Coordination Hub as the go-to contact point requires:

- **Awareness-Building:** A gradual increase in visibility through events, collaborations, and success stories.
- **Trust and Credibility:** Consistently delivering high-quality services to earn the trust of the community.
- **Adoption Metrics:** Tracking the growth in PID usage and feedback to demonstrate the hub's impact over time.

Long-Term Vision for the PID Coordination Hub

Establishing transparency as a standard practice reinforces the PID Coordination Hub's role as a trusted central contact point. It ensures that the services it promotes are not only useful but also reliable, ethical, and aligned with the broader goals of the NFDI, such as fostering FAIR data practices and creating a sustainable research infrastructure. This ongoing effort builds trust and cultivates a culture of transparency within the research ecosystem.

Tasks of the PID Coordination Hub

Based on the vision – to be the central contact point for all questions related to PIDs within NFDI –, the following tasks are derived for the PID Coordination Hub.²¹

Overview of Components

The PID Coordination Hub offers practical tools and resources to help repository managers, researchers, and other stakeholders integrate and use PIDs effectively.

²¹ Bingert et al. (2024). Proposal for the Integration Phase of Base4NFDI.

These resources, developed during the initial phase of the PID4NFDI project, will continue to be expanded and refined:

1. **Cookbook:** A guide or manual that provides step-by-step instructions and best practices for implementing and managing PIDs in repositories. It typically includes examples, troubleshooting tips, and strategies for ensuring interoperability, long-term access to data and links to the full documentation.
2. **Metadata and Interoperability Resources:** These include templates and guidelines for creating, structuring, and maintaining metadata associated with PIDs. High-quality metadata²² ensures that resources are easily discoverable, well-documented, and compatible with various systems.
3. **PID Provider Table:** A curated and comprehensive list of PIDs as well as of organizations and services that issue PIDs (e.g., DOI, ORCID, IGSN, RAiD, ePIC) serves as a basis for the PID selection guide, an overview of a curated selection of frequently used PIDs and PID services within NFDI. The public version of the table on the website²³ helps users identify appropriate PID providers based on their specific needs, such as the type of resource, metadata requirements, or regional focus.
4. **PID Selection Guide:** Building on this table, the PID selection guide, developed as a decision matrix, helps users navigate the complexities of choosing a suitable PID provider. It factors in criteria such as cost-effectiveness, governance alignment, metadata standards, and interoperability. For example, if a researcher needs a PID for a dataset with strict FAIR compliance, the guide can recommend providers with strong sustainability measures and technical capabilities that meet those needs.

Providing a PID Selection Guide

The PID selection guide will be developed based on two existing models – the PIDWijzer and the FREYA guides –, with their functionalities tailored to meet the specific needs of the NFDI community. While the existing models offer a strong foundation for the planned PID selection framework, they also exhibit certain limitations.

Existing Model 1: FREYA Guides to Choosing PIDs

The **Guides to Choosing Persistent Identifiers** developed as part of the EU project **FREYA** aim to provide structured guidance on the selection and implementation of PIDs for various research-related contexts. These guides address the diverse needs

²² Strecker (2024), pp. 21-23.

²³ <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/get-pid/services-provider/>

of research communities, emphasizing how PIDs contribute to open science and FAIR principles. The guides are presented as static decision trees and are published on the FREYAs project website as well as on Zenodo and CORDIS²⁴.

Key Aspects of the FREYA Guides:

1. Purpose-Specific Recommendations:

- They help organizations and researchers identify which PIDs fit best specific resource types, such as identifying datasets, researchers, publications, or institutions.
- Examples include **DOIs** for datasets and publications, **ORCID IDs** for researchers, **ROR IDs** for institutions, and identifiers for **software**²⁵.

2. Evaluation Criteria:

- The guides encourage evaluating PIDs based on governance, community adoption, technical specifications, metadata standards, and cost.
- They highlight factors like global interoperability, system sustainability, and the ability to track object relationships.

3. Practical Implementation Advice:

- Insights into integrating PIDs into workflows, platforms, and repositories.
- Information on existing PID registries and services.

4. Specific Use Cases and Communities:

- Guides address domains such as data management, institutional repositories, and collaborative research environments.

²⁴ You can find all project results on CORDIS: <https://doi.org/10.3030/777523> or on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3862655>. The FREYA project (2017–2020) worked to extend the PID ecosystem, fostering better connections across identifiers and improving their usability for researchers. The project contributed the PID-Forum or to tools like the PID Graph, which maps relationships between different PIDs to enhance research discoverability and tracking.

²⁵ E.g. Software Heritage PID (SWHID): <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/swh-model/persistent-identifiers.html>

Existing Model 2: PIDwijzer

The PIDwijzer is a tool developed by the Digital Heritage Network in the Netherlands to assist organizations in selecting and implementing PIDs for digital and physical resources. Its core functionality revolves around guiding users through a structured series of considerations (25 statements) to determine the most suitable PID system for their needs. This includes factors like object types, metadata requirements, technical capacity, and versioning policies. Completing the guide takes approximately 20 minutes and allows for saving and comparing results, making it useful for collaborative decision-making.²⁶

Suitable Use Cases and Communities

- **Research Communities:** The tool is particularly beneficial for institutions dealing with research outputs such as datasets, publications, audiovisual materials, and cultural heritage objects.
- **Cultural Heritage Institutions:** Museums, libraries, and archives managing diverse collections can use it to decide between systems tailored for objects versus collections.

Supported PID Systems

The guide focuses on common systems in the Netherlands, including:

- **DOIs (DataCite):** For datasets, publications, and research outputs.
- **Handles:** Flexible for various object types and metadata policies.
- **ARKs:** Known for flexibility and adaptability across domains.
- **URN:NBN:** Used primarily by libraries and archives for publications and metadata sustainability.

What is Not Included

While comprehensive, the PIDwijzer does not:

1. Provide detailed implementation support for less common international PID systems not actively used in the Netherlands.
2. Cover domain-specific nuances in great detail (e.g., EIDR for audiovisual media or CrossRef for specific publication types).
3. Address PIDs outside its target scope, such as proprietary or experimental systems not aligned with open standards.

The tool is a starting point, and its recommendations may need to be supplemented by specific NFDI community practices, cost considerations, or support requirements as it was developed with the Dutch Heritage situation in

²⁶ For more detailed information on the methodology of the PIDwijzer see: <https://www.pidwijzer.nl/en/pid-guide-methodology>

mind. The tool is open source and licensed under CC-0. Therefore, it is considered to be reused, refined and supplemented for NFDI specific requirements during the PID4NFDI project's integration phase.

Conclusion

By providing these materials as core components of a PID selection framework, repository managers and other users are equipped with the knowledge and tools to efficiently adopt PIDs, ensuring improved data management, discoverability, and compliance with FAIR principles. The challenges in PID management within NFDI arise from a fragmented ecosystem of PID providers with differing technologies, maturity levels, and governance, complicating consistent adoption across various use cases. The NFDI's project-based funding model, focused on short-term collaboration, contrasts with the long-term commitments necessary for sustainable PID management. Key actions for sustainability include incorporating PID costs into research budgets, integrating PIDs early in the research lifecycle, raising funder awareness of their cost-effectiveness, and securing long-term infrastructure support. The PID4NFDI Coordination Hub plays a crucial role in promoting best practices, encouraging alignment with standards like POSI, and facilitating the efficient, sustainable integration of PIDs throughout the research lifecycle. The Hub will be expanded and adapted to accommodate evolving NFDI PID use cases.

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